

PEDAGOGICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF PATRIOTIC EDUCATION OF YOUTH ON THE BASIS OF AXIOLOGICAL APPROACH

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Abstract: *One of the leading, main components of high spirituality is patriotism. Therefore, they approach and interpret the concept of patriotism from different angles. In our opinion, patriotism means that a person values his motherland and spends his energy and energy for this motherland, regardless of its field. Although this definition does not cover all aspects of patriotism, the definition is correctly understood if the word patriotism is approached in a broad sense. In this article, there are thoughts and opinions about educating young people in the spirit of patriotism.*

Key words: *youth, patriotism, values, loyalty, concept of homeland, education and training.*

Аннотация: *Одним из ведущих, главных компонентов высокой духовности является патриотизм. Поэтому они подходят и интерпретируют понятие патриотизма с разных сторон. На наш взгляд, патриотизм означает, что человек дорожит своей Родиной и тратит свою энергию и энергию на эту Родину, независимо от ее сферы. Хотя это определение не охватывает все аспекты патриотизма, оно правильно понимается, если подходить к слову патриотизм в широком смысле. В данной статье есть мысли и мнения о воспитании молодежи в духе патриотизма.*

Ключевые слова: молодежь, патриотизм, ценности, лояльность, понятие Родины, воспитание и воспитание.

INTRODUCTION

The problem of raising the young generation of new Uzbekistan in the spirit of patriotism is one of the urgent issues in the way of the development of our country. Today, due to the global changes taking place not only geographically and geopolitically, but also in all aspects of the life of our society, this problem is gaining special importance. So, let's try to define the problem with questions: What are the goals of modern patriotic education? What topics are covered within the framework of patriotic education? How often are patriotic education classes organized?

The modern geopolitical, social, economic, interethnic situation in Uzbekistan has changed the problem of educating young people in the spirit of patriotism. The main reason for this situation, unfortunately, is the high activity of forms of collective recreation that attract young people not with the idea of the general well-being of the country or with the content of personal growth. Convenience, "democracy", freedom of speech and movement.

The relevance of this problem is related to society's need for patriotic education of young people, which is of particular importance for several reasons:

- the level of awareness of the young generation (often negative) is increasing;
- in addition, the manifestation of "democratization" processes and "free" activities in order to collect all kinds of buzz, jokes and likes for content on social networks that will bring a lot of income. All this, in turn, creates certain difficulties for the young generation to understand the essence of freedom of speech and movement and, as a result, the sense of patriotism itself;
- modern youth did not go through specific situations, schools, or the movement of patriotic education familiar to the representatives of the older generation.

METHODOLOGY AND DISCUSSION OF THE PROBLEM

Folk wisdom, national ideals and ideas, which are the foundation of national consciousness, dignity, and self-respect, should occupy an important place in the educational process. Patriotic beliefs include knowledge combined with a sincere belief in one's own truth. Scientists define patriotic education as "perfect, developed, highly educated, socially active and nationally conscious, deep civic responsibility, healthy intellectual, creative and spiritual qualities, kinship and patriotic feelings, hard work, economic they understand it as "forming a person with intelligence, initiative and hard work". [8, 3 p.].

The great teacher and thinker Ya.A.

Comenius, "they could defend everything they believed to be true and good ... honestly" [3, p. 276].

In addition to feelings and beliefs, activity is needed – this is an important aspect of patriotic education. Patriotic activities include:

- to connect deeply with the people, to participate in their goals and common affairs, to care about their well-being;
- preserving and improving the culture, traditions, customs, rituals of the motherland; compliance with moral standards and rules developed by the people, state laws;
- to have knowledge about the symbols of one's homeland;
- strengthening the statehood of one's people;
- activities aimed at strengthening the belonging of one's country and readiness to protect it;
- knowledge of the history of one's family, people, dependence on the places where one grew up;
- the ability to conscientiously perform one's duties, to work creatively [6, p. 81].

Today, educating the youth of New Uzbekistan in the spirit of patriotism should become the main element of the educational work of educational institutions. Now

let's try to consider several issues related to patriotic education based on national values. What are the goals, forms and methods of organizing the patriotic education of preschool children, schoolchildren and students of vocational colleges, as well as higher educational institutions?

The content of the concept of patriotism in the Union reflects the basic concepts of "Motherland" and "Motherland". The same concepts are related, on the one hand, to a person's attachment to his motherland, and on the other hand, to the socio-economic, political, cultural and other characteristics of each society.

The main principles of patriotism in modern conditions:

- harmonizing the personal importance of patriotism with society;
- directing the education of patriotism based on national values not only to the future, but also to the present;
- development of national identity together with internationalist and tolerance; - to understand the importance of basic concepts such as "Motherland", "Motherland", "People" that determine inclusion of patriotism in the category of socio-spiritual values.

Patriotism is a social and spiritual value of every nation, as well as an integral part of the social and moral formation of a person, and the following can be considered:

- cognitive level (moral or political principle);
- emotional level (moral feeling);
- level of behavior (integrative moral quality).

In determining the sense of patriotism, it is of particular importance to strengthen the connection between the personal significance of patriotism and patriotism with social significance. Love for the country as a high spiritual and moral feeling determines the needs of the society for the needs of the individual, i.e. the patriot.

A patriot is a person who loves his country, is loyal to his country and people, and strives to benefit from his work.

The feeling of patriotism expresses the purely personal attitude of each person to his motherland, to the Motherland, in other words. Love for the country is an object of value relationship, that is, patriotism is an “objective” as well as a “subjective” value. As an objective value, patriotism is considered as a good, true and just phenomenon. As a subjective value, it represents the normative ideas consolidated in public consciousness and culture.

The transformation of national, national and social values into personal values is carried out on the basis of the active activity of the individual. These forms of activity are manifested in various areas of human life. The educational and labor activity of every citizen of the country is of particular importance, during which social experience is shared and the system of this society is mastered.

Patriotic education is a process of mutual relations between pedagogues and pupils, teachers and students aimed at forming and improving the feeling of patriotism, patriotic beliefs and stable norms of patriotic behavior. All manifestations of patriotism are a desire to be useful, to a specific need. Patriotism, like collectivism, includes unity and diversity of personal and social goals, cooperation and human interaction. Therefore, the individual is not only himself

Attention to “I”, but also to other people, is manifested in the desire to interact and benefit. Consequently, it is manifested in a person’s understanding and fulfillment of his patriotic duty to his country and people.

In the context of the concept of patriotism in modern conditions, the unity of the public and personal interests of a person, a citizen, is absolutely unchangeable and irreplaceable.

RESULTS

The goal of educating young people in the spirit of patriotism is to educate a patriotic person who loves his motherland, is bravely devoted to his people, is ready to serve him with his work and protect his interests in the way of creativity and prosperity.

The tasks of educating young people of new Uzbekistan in the spirit of patriotism:

- formation and development of patriotic feelings;
- improvement of patriotic knowledge, belief, personal opinion and character based on national values;
- formation of skills necessary for independent activity of a patriotic nature.

Taking into account the above, it is legal to include the following components in the content of the concept of “patriotism”:

- Love for the motherland, native land, native language;
- to respect the past of one’s country, the traditions and customs of one’s people, to know the history of the country, to understand the tasks facing the country and the duty of patriotism;
- respect for other peoples, their traditions and culture, intolerance of racial and national enmity;
- Striving to strengthen the honor and dignity of the Motherland, respect for the army and readiness to defend the Motherland;
- Willingness to serve the interests of the country, active and conscious participation in labor activities, combining personal and public interests.

The development of children and youth according to standards should include citizenship, patriotism, spiritual and moral, aesthetic, physical, labor and environmental education.

Young generations are tasked with forming systematic knowledge about the place of Uzbekistan in the world geopolitical, economic and cultural space, the importance of the development strategy of New Uzbekistan, its historical place and territorial integrity. In this regard, patriotic, spiritual and moral events are becoming especially relevant.

Patriotic education of preschool children

- Reading a work of oral folk art
- Conducting interviews

- Learning proverbs, poems and songs about the homeland

Education of school children in the spirit of patriotism

- Ceremonial raising of the state symbols flag, singing of the national anthem

- Celebrate national holidays and important dates for the entire country

Holding classes on the topic of “Patriotism”.

- Organization of various circles

Education of students of vocational colleges and HEIs in the spirit of patriotism

- Organization of various actions, teams

- Conducting special promotions

- Introduction of primary military training

CONCLUSION

The main directions of raising children in the spirit of patriotism are as follows:

- family – formation of ideas about family, clan and offspring;

- getting to know social events; formation of knowledge about state history, state symbols;

- getting to know the traditions and culture of one’s people; - formation of knowledge about the motherland.

Before high school, when the child’s interest in the social world and social events is especially active, it is convenient to start systematic patriotic education. [6, 11 p.].

However, it is not enough to consider patriotism only as a socio-historical phenomenon based on specific socio-political and economic characteristics of this or that society. It cannot be denied that there are “natural” foundations of patriotism among young people, which are formed independently of the above factors and characterize certain layers of a person’s spiritual life: love for one’s motherland, love for one’s motherland. Respect for the language, people, traditions and customs, etc.

Naturally, this cannot be determined by the innate features of the psyche, but it is also impossible not to take this factor into account when describing patriotism.

“It’s easier to awaken a sense of patriotism,” N. Moiseyuk says, “if you focus the student’s attention on the real changes taking place in his family, native village, city.” Ladi Therefore, pedagogues lead the student to act only by sharpening his feelings and relying on them” [5, 247 p.]. As a result of the activity, behavioral skills and habits become the norm in the process of repetition. The system of actions, behavior gradually becomes a character trait, becomes a property of a person [5, 247 p.].

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